

RECYCLING OF END-OF-LIFE WIND TURBINE BLADES INTO POLYMER COMPOSITES: EFFECT OF REPROCESSING ON SECONDARY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The increase in composite waste from decommissioned wind turbine blades must be managed through recycling to alleviate environmental issues. To provide a competitive alternative to traditional virgin composites, this study investigates the potential use of waste wind turbine blades (WWTB) as a sustainable reinforcement material in secondary polypropylene (PP) composites. WWTB and a coupling agent (maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene, or MAPP) were combined to create PP composites through extrusion and injection moulding. To assess their recyclability and performance retention, these composites underwent three reprocessing cycles, which included the addition of manufacturing waste produced during extrusion. The samples were characterized using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), tensile test, three-point bending test, and melt flow index (MFI). Due to the compatibilization, the composites exhibited an increase in mechanical properties compared to both uncompatibilized composites and pure PP. The reprocessed composites in the second and third cycles further exhibited improved mechanical performance, attributed to lower melt temperature and screw speed during injection moulding. FTIR analysis revealed that the functional groups remained unaffected across reprocessing cycles. Upon MAPP addition, DSC revealed higher melting points and crystallinity of composites, and reprocessing had little effect on the degree of crystallinity. Furthermore, following repeated reprocessing, the MFI values increased, suggesting a reduction in the molecular weights of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) has increased its growth estimate for 2024–2030 (1210GW) by 10% [1]. The onshore installed capacity is expected to reach over 5000 GW by 2050, with offshore contributing 1000 GW [2]. As the wind energy industry grows, 330,000 t/year of composite materials manufactured from wind turbine blades will be deposited or burned globally until 2028, and 418,000 t/year between 2028 and 2040 [3]. Circularity of materials has received more attention from industry and scholars in recent years, especially in the wind energy sector, which generates enormous amounts of outdated turbine components, such as blades [4].

Steel, copper wire, hardware, and outfitting make up 85% of wind turbine components. The remaining 15% consists mostly of waste glass or carbon fibre composites from wind turbines, which are environmentally hazardous due to their 60% reinforcing fibre and 40% resin content. The cross-linked polymer chains of thermoset resins, such as polyester and epoxy, further complicate recycling. Recycling such composite wastes is quite challenging since these blades have been designed to endure extreme mechanical and environmental stresses for many years [2], [5], [6]. Recent years have seen several studies on the recycling of waste fiber-reinforced epoxy resins (WFREs) by pyrolysis [7] and chemical treatment [3], emphasizing the breakdown of epoxy resins to recover high-value carbon fibers. However, thorough research is still needed to recover glass fibers using these two techniques.

On the other hand, mechanical recycling, which involves grinding the composite to generate a mixture of single fibres, resin chunks, and fibre matting embedded in resin, is one of the simplest methods for handling decommissioned blades out of all the recycling systems now in use [8]. Due to its lower energy consumption of 0.1–4.8 MJ/kg and lower process cost compared to the value of recycled material, mechanical recycling is the most sought-after recycling method among industries [9].

In 2024, Pu et al. developed polypropylene composites via injection moulding by using wind turbine blade waste as a filler up to 50 wt% along with other compatibilizers. These composites exhibited a significant increase of 37.3% of tensile strength, 147.3% of tensile modulus, and 165.5% of flexural strength [10]. Similarly, Mamanpush et al. used such wind turbine blade waste as a feedstock alongside high-density polyethylene (HDPE) to extrude profiled composites. Such secondary composites showed improved mechanical and physical properties and further proving the potential capability of using waste wind turbine blades in secondary polymer composites [11].

However, the price of virgin glass fibre, which is approximately €2/kg [12] should be considered while recycling glass fibers from wind turbine blades. The lower energy demand for recycling (10–20 times lower) compared to the embodied energy of manufacturing for virgin glass (13–32 MJ/kg) [13] is equally imperative. To tackle such competitiveness in the raw materials, many investigations have been done in the past related to the reprocessing capability of glass fibre reinforced polypropylene composites. Colucci et al. investigated how recycling affected the performance behaviour of virgin glass fibre/polypropylene composites using injection moulding. However, the samples were only mechanically recycled once, and the mechanical characteristics were found to be lower than those of non-recycled polypropylene [14]. Chen et al. investigated the impact of three (3) injection moulding machine processing cycles on the characteristics of long glass fibre and PP. Their results demonstrated that the thermo-mechanical, rheological, and thermal characteristics of the composite are not significantly affected by mechanical recycling [15]. A similar investigation of reprocessing was done by Touati et al. on isotactic polypropylene (PP)/Cloisite 15A (OMMT) (5 wt.%) nanocomposites in the presence of maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene used as a compatibilizer [16]. Achukwu et al. confirmed that glass fibre reinforced polypropylene composites can be reprocessed for a maximum of 3 cycles without significant deterioration of mechanical properties or chemical structure [17].

Up until now, research on the reprocessing of glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene (GF-PP) composites has mostly focused on systems that use virgin glass fibres; similarly, manufacturing waste produced during the reprocessing process has received less attention. Therefore, to make the secondary composites more competitive against virgin composites, the current study examines the effects of 3 reprocessing cycles on secondary polypropylene composites reinforced with waste from shredded wind turbine blades, a non-virgin, post-industrial source of glass fibre. And to better replicate actual recycling situations, this work not only uses the recycled reinforcement but also ingeniously combines manufacturing waste generated during extrusion with the shredded secondary composites. For fair comparison, these composites were compared with pure PP.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

For the fabrication of the novel secondary polymer composites, a primary raw material, specifically mechanically recycled waste wind turbine blade (WWTB), was obtained from PreZero Gestion De Residuos SA (Spain), exhibiting a particle size of below 20 mm. It was further sieved, and the size fraction above 500 µm was considered for extrusion. The matrix utilized in this work is a thermoplastic polymer, specifically polypropylene (SABIC PP 520P), acquired from Resinex (Netherlands). At 2.16 kg of load and 230°C, the melt flow rate of PP is 10.5 g/10min. A coupling agent, maleic anhydride-graft-polypropylene (MAPP), was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Netherlands).

2.2 Composite preparation and reprocessing

Different formulations (*Table 1*) of PP and WWTB were used to produce new secondary composites using two major processing methods: twin-screw extrusion and injection moulding. At first, the primary and secondary feeders of twin screw extruder (HAAKE Rheomex OS twin screw, ThermoFischer) were supplied with PP + MAPP and WWTB, respectively at 110 rpm rotation speed at processing temperatures of 180 °C for zone 1 and zone 2, 190 °C for zone 3 up to zone 8 and 200 °C for zone 9 and zone 10. Thoroughly compounded granules or pellets were extruded for three different cycles. Then, the dried pellets were used to produce tensile (75 mm × 5 mm × 2 mm) and bending specimens (80 mm × 10 mm × 4 mm) using a BOY XS injection moulding. The following parameters were used for injection moulding: melt temperature (200 °C), mould temperature (210 °C), injection speed (110 mm/s), injection time (15 s), cooling time (15 s), and cycle time (120 s).

In the first cycle, virgin PP was compounded with WWTB to produce secondary composites without a coupling agent. Similarly, for composites with a coupling agent, MAPP was compounded with virgin PP and WWTB (*Figure 2*). Later, a similar procedure was used for an additional two cycles, where the shredded composites, along with the corresponding pellets from the same cycle, which can be considered as manufacturing waste, were compounded to produce new composites. For instance, to produce a second cycle composite, tested samples from the first cycle were shredded and mixed with the pellets of corresponding composition from the first cycle, which are then extruded and injection moulded into second cycle composites, as shown in *Figure 1*.

From here on, the following nomenclature has been adopted for each composition: XA/YB/ZC, where X corresponds to the concentration of polypropylene by weight, Y to the recycled material from WWTB by weight, and Z to the coupling agent by weight. Similarly, A, B, and C correspond to the short names of the material. For instance, 73PP/25RM/2CA is a formulation with 73 wt.% of polypropylene, 25 wt.% of recycled material from WWTB, and 2 wt.% of coupling agent.

Figure 1: Illustration of the reprocessing method for each cycle

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the reprocessing of secondary composites

Table 1: Formulation of secondary polymer composites

Sample	Polypropylene (wt.%)	Recycled material (wt.%)	Coupling agent (wt.%)
100PP	100	0	0
75PP/25RM	75	25	0
50PP/50RM	50	50	0
73PP/25RM/2CA	73	25	2
48PP/50RM/2CA	48	50	2
70PP/25RM/5CA	70	25	5
45PP/50RM/5CA	45	50	5

2.3 Characterization

Chemical (structural) analysis

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR): This technique was employed to characterise the functional groups present in the secondary composites after multiple reprocessing cycles. Using the Frontier Spectrometer from Perkin Elmer, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was conducted in the range of 400 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ with 20 scans per measurement.

Thermal analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC): The degree of crystallinity (X_c), melting and crystallization behaviours of all the extruded samples were determined using DSC – Q2000 (TA Instruments Co., Ltd., USA). The analysis was carried out in a temperature range between -90 °C and 220 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 50 mL/min and employing 5 °C/min for both heating and cooling cycles. All the samples were subjected to two heating and one cooling cycle. The following equation was used in the calculation of X_c :

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^*} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where ΔH_m denotes the melting enthalpy of the PP in the composition and ΔH_m^* enthalpy of melting of fully crystalline PP, taken as 209 J/kg [18].

Mechanical testing

Tensile and three-point bending test: To determine the tensile and flexural properties of the injection moulded composites, both tensile and three-point bending tests were conducted according to ISO 527 – 2 and ISO 178, respectively, using a Zwick Roell ZW010 equipped with a 2.5 kN load cell. The standard test parameters of 5 mm/min and 10 mm/min cross-head speed were used for the tensile test and bending test, respectively. However, tensile testing of third-cycle PP was conducted at a cross-head speed of 50mm/min. The flexural tests were carried out up to 10% deformation. The results were determined based on the average of five samples for each composition.

Rheology

Melt flow rate (MFR): Measurement of the MFI for all the extruded samples was performed according to ISO 1133-1 (Method A) with Cflow Extrusion Plastometer (Zwick Roell 4100). A standard method by using an applied weight of 2.16 kg at 230 °C was used. Melt flow rate (MFR) was calculated according to equation (2):

$$MFR = \frac{600m}{t} \quad (2)$$

Where m denotes the average mass, in grams, of the cut-offs, and t denotes the cut-off time interval, in seconds

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical (structural) analysis

The possible chemical structure changes within the composites for different reprocessing cycles were examined by FT-IR spectra (*Figure 3*). In all the reprocessing cycles of PP, the medium CH₂ bending vibration was observed at 1457 cm⁻¹, whereas the C–H stretch bond is represented by the absorption band at 2950 cm⁻¹. Also, CH₃ bending vibrations were obtained approximately at 1375 cm⁻¹ [17]. Touati et al. also reported a weak intensity carbonyl band that represents MAPP compatibilizer at 1720 cm⁻¹ and the FT-IR spectra of pure PP did not show this carbonyl band [16]. The stretching vibration of the Si-O bonds inside SiO₂ is responsible for the peak at 1100 cm⁻¹ [10]. Similar results were observed by several researchers, which indicate that no significant structural change, such as oxidative degradation, has occurred even after multiple reprocessing cycles of reinforced PP composites [16], [17], [19].

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of all the composites at different reprocessing cycles

Thermal analysis

The DSC thermograms, as shown in *Figure 4* represent the melting and cooling curves of all the extruded samples for different reprocessing cycles. The melting point of pure PP in the first cycle was 162.91 °C. However, with the addition of WWTB, the melting point of the composites 75PP25RM and 50PP50RM increased to 165 °C. Meanwhile, after the compatibilization, the melting points of the composites were reduced. A similar behaviour was observed by Hassan et al [18].

The ΔH_m is an essential parameter since its value is directly correlated with the polymer's total crystallinity content [20]. Similar to Hassan et al. report, ΔH_m of both uncompatibilized and compatibilized composites reduced compared to pure PP, which is attributed to the reduction of the degree of crystallinity of the PP matrix with the incorporation of fibres. The incorporation of glass fibres disrupts the linear crystallizable arrangement of the PP chains, resulting in a reduced degree of crystallinity and an increased proportion of flexible amorphous material[18]. On the other hand, the integration of MAPP into the composites has enhanced the level of crystallinity, which indicates that the coupling agent's presence has enhanced the matrix nucleation [21], [22]. In addition, Pu et al. reported that the composites with a lower amount of WWTB augment the crystallinity due to the nucleation-inducing effect of WWTB, which can be seen from *Figure 5*. However, the increased viscosity at larger WWTB contents prevented PP chains from arranging regularly, which resulted in a noticeable reduction in crystallinity [10].

The melting and crystallization points of compatibilized and uncompatibilized composites had an insignificant decrease after three cycles, except PP, where melting and crystallization points increased as the number of reprocessing cycles increased. The crystallinity index of all the composites, including PP, exhibited a negligible reduction after the second cycle extrusion, however, the X_c of PP after the second cycle was not considered here due to an inappropriate value. In the third cycle, X_c of PP had a slight reduction compared to the first cycle. Meanwhile, X_c of all the other composites either had a slight improvement or similar values even after three reprocessing cycles.

Figure 4: DSC thermograms of all the composites at different reprocessing cycles: (a, c, e) melting; (b, d, f) crystallization

Figure 5: Crystallinity index of all the composites at different reprocessing cycles

Mechanical testing

Tensile properties

The tensile properties of the first cycle secondary composites, such as 75PP25RM, which are WWTB reinforced PP composites, had a similar tensile strength to pure PP, with a higher stiffness. However, further reductions in tensile strength were observed with increased recycled material content. The 50PP50RM composites exhibited a lower tensile strength due to poor interfacial strength between the matrix and recycled fibre from WWTB, which consists of epoxy residue on its surface. For this reason, it can be assumed that the stress applied cannot be transferred from the matrix to the fibres [23]. However, the problem of poor adhesion was addressed with the addition of a coupling agent, which led to a slight improvement of 9% in those composites after the addition of 2 wt% (48PP50RM2CA) and 5 wt% (70PP25RM5CA) coupling agent compared to pure PP. Moreover, the higher weight percentage of CA showed an improvement in the stiffness of the composite while maintaining a good tensile strength, as shown in *Figure 6*.

In the second and third cycles, the tensile properties of all the composites, including pure PP, have been increased compared to their counterparts from the first cycle. According to Huang et al. this improvement in the tensile could be attributed to several processing factors of injection moulding such as lower screw speed and lower melt temperature. Less damage to the PP molecular chains results in higher molecular densities and which in turn increases the tensile strength of reprocessed composites. Similarly, at lower melt temperature, the arrangement of molecular chains will not disorganize, resulting in higher tensile strength [24].

Figure 6: Tensile strength (a) and Tensile modulus (b) of different composites at three reprocessing cycles

Flexural properties

Unlike tensile properties, there were some significant improvements in the flexural properties of the secondary composites, even without a CA, over pure PP, as shown in *Figure 7*. In the first cycle, the flexural strengths showed an increase in all the composites, with 50PP50RM and 45PP50RM5CA exhibiting the highest changes of 18% and 21%, respectively. However, the samples without a CA had high stiffness, as indicated by their higher flexural modulus compared to all the other samples with a coupling agent, which shows the positive effect of using a CA on the secondary composites. The second cycle composites, however, exhibited an improvement in their flexural properties. All the second-cycle composites showed an increase in flexural strength compared to their counterparts from the first cycle. The flexural modulus of all the composites with a CA, except 45PP50RM5CA, was increased, making them stiffer than the composites without a CA, which had a lower flexural modulus compared to the first

cycle. Despite having a reduction in the flexural strength in the third cycle, these composites performed better than their counterparts from the first cycle. Similar observations were made in terms of flexural modulus. Again, these improvements can be attributed to the processing parameters of injection moulding.

Figure 7: Flexural strength (a) and Flexural modulus (b) of different composites at three reprocessing cycles

Rheology

Melt flow index (MFI)

The MFI of composites was determined to study the effects of reprocessing on viscosity and molecular weight. Figure 8 shows the MFI of pure PP and different composites with and without CA for three reprocessing cycles. For pure PP, MFI progressively increased with every reprocessing cycle, beginning from 10.5 g/10min up to 13.2 g/10min in the third cycle, resulting in a 25% increase. A similar trend was observed with all the other composites, suggesting a decrease in the molecular weight of polypropylene during the three reprocessing cycles.

Figure 8: MFI properties of different secondary composites subjected to three reprocessing cycles

In addition, an increasing trend of MFI was observed with the higher dosage of CA in the composites. The highest increase of MFI of 41% was observed for the 70PP25RM2CA composite when it was reprocessed for the third time. The Ara'ujo et al. confirm that an increase in the MFI results in a drop in the melt viscosity and, as a result, a negative change in the molecular weight of the plastic and also noticed that reduction in intermolecular interaction and entanglements results in a decrease in polymer viscosity, which in turn causes a decrease in molecular weight and polymer chain length [25]. Spicker et al. also showed that their PP subjected to ten reprocessing cycles had improved MFI, decreased average molecular weight and viscosity, all of which corresponded to the occurrence of β -scission reactions [26].

4 CONCLUSIONS

In order to make the secondary polymer composites more competitive against virgin composites, reinforcement from WWTB was used to prepare PP composites via injection moulding and thereafter subjected to 3 reprocessing cycles along with manufacturing waste derived during extrusion. The resulting polymer composites were examined in terms of their mechanical, thermal, rheological, and structural properties. Therefore, it may be concluded that:

- The addition of coupling agent (MAPP) to the secondary composites showed a positive effect of 9% improvement in tensile strength of 48PP50RM2CA and 70PP25RM5CA. Similarly, a 21% improvement was seen in the flexural strength of 45PP50RM5CA. Higher amounts of WWTB and MAPP had a positive impact on the mechanical properties. In 2nd and 3rd cycle composites, tensile and flexural properties were further improved, which can be attributed to the lower screw speed and melt temperature of injection moulding;
- FT-IR spectra showed that functional groups present in the composites were unaffected even after 3 reprocessing cycles, which proves that the degradation is thermo-mechanical, not thermo-oxidative;
- Melting points of uncompatibilized composites were increased to 165 °C. The integration of MAPP into the composites has enhanced the degree of crystallinity, which indicates that the coupling agent's presence has enhanced the matrix nucleation. In all the composites, including pure PP, a slight reduction or similar degree of crystallinity was observed even after 3 reprocessing cycles;
- The MFI of all the composites was increased after 3 reprocessing cycles, suggesting a decreased viscosity and lower molecular weight, all of which happened due to the β -scission reactions.

The findings of this study demonstrate the potential of waste wind turbine blades (WWTB) as a viable reinforcement material in secondary polypropylene composites. The ability of these composites to undergo reprocessing with performance trends comparable to those reinforced with virgin glass fibres highlights their promise as a competitive and sustainable alternative to conventional virgin composites. Furthermore, a detailed comparative study has to be done between these secondary composites and virgin PP-GF composites.

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